

On Soft slightly πg -continuous functions

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce and study the concept of soft slightly πg -continuous functions which is weaker than soft πg -continuous functions and obtain its fundamental properties. The relationship between soft slightly πg -continuity and other related functions is also analyzed.

Keywords: Soft πg -closed set; soft πg -open set; soft clopen set; soft πg -Continuity; soft slightly continuity; soft slightly πg -continuity.

1. Introduction

Molodtsov [8] initiated the concept of soft set theory as a new mathematical tool and presented the fundamental results of the soft sets. Muhammad Shabir and Munazza Naz [10] introduced soft topological spaces and the notions of soft open sets, soft closed sets, soft closure, soft interior points, soft neighborhood of a point and soft separation axioms. Kharal et al. [5] introduced soft function over classes of soft sets. Cigdem Gunduz Aras et al., [1] in 2013 studied and discussed the properties of Soft continuous mappings which are defined over an initial universe set with a fixed set of parameters. In this paper, soft slightly πg -continuity is introduced and studied. Moreover, basic properties for soft slightly πg -continuous functions are investigated and relationship between soft slightly πg -continuous functions and its graphs are studied.

2. Preliminaries

Definition: 2.1[8]

Let U be the initial universe and $P(U)$ denote the power set of U . Let E denote the set of all parameters. Let A be a non-empty subset of E . A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U , where F is a mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow P(U)$.

Definition: 2.2[6]

A subset (A, E) of a topological space X is called soft generalized-closed (soft g -closed), if $cl(A, E) \tilde{\subset} (U, E)$ whenever $(A, E) \tilde{\subset} (U, E)$ and (U, E) is soft open in X .

Definition: 2.3[2]

A subset (A, E) of a topological space X is called soft regular closed, if $cl(int(A, E)) = (A, E)$. The complement of soft regular closed set is soft regular open set.

Definition: 2.4[2]

The finite union of soft regular open sets is said to be soft π -open. The complement of soft π -open is said to be soft π -closed.

Definition: 2.5[2]

A subset (A, E) of a topological space X is called soft πg -closed in a soft topological space (X, τ, E) , if $cl(A, E) \tilde{\subset} (U, E)$ whenever $(A, E) \tilde{\subset} (U, E)$ and (U, E) is soft π -open in X .

Definition: 2.6[1]

Let (F, E) be a soft set over X . The soft set (F, E) is called soft point, denoted by (x_e, E) , if for element $e \in E$, $F(e) = \{x\}$ and $F(e') = \emptyset$ for all $e' \in E - \{e\}$.

Definition: 2.7[11]

Let (X, τ, E) and (Y, τ', E) be two topological spaces. A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is said to be Soft Semi continuous (Soft pre-continuous, Soft α -continuous, Soft β -continuous), if $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft semi open (soft pre-open, soft α -open, soft β -open) in (X, τ, E) for every soft open set (G, E) of (Y, τ', E) .

Definition: 2.8[3]

Let (X, τ, E) and (Y, τ', E) be two topological spaces. A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is said to be Soft regular continuous (Soft π -continuous, Soft g -continuous, Soft πg -continuous), if $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft regular open (soft π -open, soft g -open, soft πg -open) in (X, τ, E) for every soft open set (G, E) of (Y, τ', E) .

Definition: 2.9[3]

A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft πg -irresolute, if $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -open in (X, τ, E) for every soft πg -open set (G, E) of (Y, τ', E) .

Definition: 2.10[2]

A space (X, τ, E) is called soft πg - $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ [6], if every soft πg -closed set is soft closed, or equivalently every soft πg -open set is soft open.

Definition: 2.11[10]

A soft topological space (X, τ, E) is a soft $-T_0$ space, if for each pair of distinct soft points x and y in X , there exist soft open sets (F, E) and (G, E) such that $x \in (F, E)$ and $y \notin (F, E)$ or $y \in (G, E)$ and $x \notin (G, E)$.

Definition: 2.12[3]

A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is called $\tilde{S}\pi g$ -open, if image of each open set in X is $\tilde{S}\pi g$ -open in Y .

Definition: 2.13[4]

A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is called soft contra πg -continuous, if $f^{-1}(F, E)$ is soft πg -closed in X for every soft open set (F, E) of Y .

Definition: 2.14[4]

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft πg -compact, if every soft πg -open cover of X has a finite sub cover.

Definition: 2.15[4]

Soft countably πg -compact, if every soft πg -open countably cover of X has a finite subcover.

Definition: 2.16[4]

soft πg -Lindelöf, if every soft πg -open cover of X has a countable subcover.

Definition: 2.17[4]

A space (X, τ, E) is called soft πg -connected provided that X cannot be written as the union of two disjoint non-empty soft πg -open sets.

Definition: 2.18[10]

A soft topological space (X, τ, E) is a soft πg - T_0 space, if for each pair of distinct soft points x and y in X , there exist soft open sets (F, E) and (G, E) such that $x \in (F, E)$ and $y \notin (F, E)$ or $y \in (G, E)$ and $x \notin (G, E)$.

3. Slightly πg -continuous functions

Definition: 3.1

A function $f : (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is called soft slightly continuous, if $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft open in X for each soft clopen subset (G, E) of Y .

Definition: 3.2

A function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is said to be soft slightly πg -continuous, if $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -open in X for each soft clopen subset (G, E) of Y .

Theorem: 3.3

The following statements are equivalent for a function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$

1. f is soft slightly πg -continuous.
2. for every soft clopen subset (G, E) of Y , $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -closed in X .
3. for every soft clopen subset (G, E) of Y , $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -clopen in X .

Proof:

(1) \implies (2)

Let (G, E) be soft clopen in Y . Then $Y \setminus (G, E)$ is soft clopen in Y . Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(Y \setminus (G, E))$ is soft πg -open in X . $f^{-1}(Y \setminus (G, E)) = X - f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -open in X implies $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -closed in X .

(2) \implies (3)

Let (G, E) be soft clopen in Y . Then $Y \setminus (G, E)$ is soft clopen in Y . By (2) $f^{-1}(Y \setminus (G, E))$ is soft πg -closed in X . Hence $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -open in X implies $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -clopen in X .

(3) \implies (1): obvious

Theorem: 3.4

Every soft slightly continuous function is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Proof: Obvious.

Remark: 3.5

The converse of the above theorem is not true in general as shown in the following examples.

Example 3.6

Let $X = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$, $Y = \{h_1, h_2, h_3\}$, $E = \{e_1, e_2\}$. Let F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4 and G_1, G_2 are functions from E to $P(X)$ and E to $P(Y)$ are defined as follows:

$F_1(e_1) = \{h_3\}$, $F_1(e_2) = \{h_1\}$; $F_2(e_1) = \{h_4\}$, $F_2(e_2) = \{h_2\}$; $F_3(e_1) = \{h_3, h_4\}$, $F_3(e_2) = \{h_1, h_2\}$; $F_4(e_1) = \{h_1, h_4\}$, $F_4(e_2) = \{h_2, h_4\}$ $F_5(e_1) = \{h_2, h_3, h_4\}$, $F_5(e_2) = \{h_1, h_2, h_3\}$; $F_6(e_1) = \{h_1, h_3, h_4\}$, $F_6(e_2) = \{h_1, h_2, h_4\}$ and $G_1(e_1) = \{h_1\}$, $G_1(e_2) = \{h_1\}$; $G_2(e_1) = \{h_2, h_3\}$, $G_2(e_2) = \{h_2, h_3\}$. Then $\tau = \{\tilde{\emptyset}, \tilde{X}, (F_1, E), (F_2, E), (F_3, E), (F_4, E), (F_5, E), (F_6, E)\}$ is a soft topological space over X and $\tau' = \{\tilde{\emptyset}, \tilde{Y}, (G_1, E), (G_2, E)\}$ is a soft topological space over Y . If the function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is defined as $f(h_1) = h_1$, $f(h_3) = h_2$ then f is soft slightly πg -continuous but not soft slightly continuous.

Theorem: 3.7

Let (X, τ, E) be a soft $\pi g-T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ space. Then the function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous if and only if it is soft slightly continuous.

Proof:

Let (G, E) be soft clopen in Y . Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft πg -open in X implies $f^{-1}(G, E)$ is soft open in X . Therefore f is soft slightly continuous. Conversely every soft slightly continuous is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 3.8

Suppose $\tilde{S}\pi GO(X)$ is soft closed under arbitrary unions. Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be a function. Then f is soft slightly πg -continuous if and only if for each point $x \in X$ and each soft clopen set (V, E) containing $f(x)$, there exists a soft πg -open set (U, E) containing x such that $f(U, E) \tilde{c} (V, E)$.

Proof:

Let $x \in X$ and (V, E) be soft clopen then $f(x) \in (V, E)$. Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous,

$f^{-1}(V, E)$ is soft πg -open in X . If we put $(U, E) = f^{-1}(V, E)$ then $x \in (U, E)$ and $f(U, E) \subseteq (V, E)$. Conversely let (V, E) be a soft clopen subset of Y and let $x \in f^{-1}(V, E)$. Since $f(x) \in (V, E)$, there exists a soft πg -open set (U_x, E) in X containing x such that $(U_x, E) \subseteq f^{-1}(V, E)$. We obtain $f^{-1}(V, E) = \cup\{(U_x, E): x \in f^{-1}(V, E)\}$. Thus $f^{-1}(V, E)$ is soft πg -open.

Definition: 3.9

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft locally indiscrete, if every soft open set of X is soft closed in X .

Theorem : 3.10

If a function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous and (Y, τ', E) is soft locally indiscrete, then f is soft πg -continuous.

Proof:

Let (A, E) be a soft open set in Y . Since Y is soft locally indiscrete, every soft open set is soft closed. Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(A, E)$ is soft πg -open in X . Hence f is soft slightly continuous.

Theorem: 3.11

If a function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous and (X, τ, E) is soft $\pi g-T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ space then f is soft slightly continuous.

Proof:

Let (A, E) be a soft clopen set in Y . By hypothesis $f^{-1}(A, E)$ is soft πg -open in X . Since X is soft $\pi g-T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ space, $f^{-1}(A, E)$ is soft open in X . Hence f is soft slightly continuous.

Definition: 3.12

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft submaximal, if each soft dense subset of X is soft open.

Definition: 3.13

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft extremally disconnected, if the soft closure of each soft open set of X is soft open in X .

Definition: 3.14

The graph $G(f)$ of a function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is said to be soft slightly πg -graph, if for each $(x, y) \in (X \times Y) \setminus G(f)$, there exist a soft πg -open set (A, E) in X containing x and a soft clopen set (B, E) in Y containing y such that $(A \times B, E) \cap G(f) = \emptyset$.

Theorem: 3.15

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be soft function and let $g: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (X \times Y, \tau \times \tau', E)$ be the soft graph function of f , defined by $g(x) = (x, f(x))$ for every $x \in X$. Then f is soft slightly πg -continuous, if g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Proof:

Let $(V, E) \in \tilde{S}CO(Y)$ then $X \times (V, E) \in \tilde{S}CO(X \times Y)$. Since g is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(V, E) = g^{-1}(X \times (V, E)) \in \tilde{S}\pi GO(X)$. Thus f is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 3.16

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be soft slightly πg -continuous function and let $g: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (X \times Y, \tau \times \tau', E)$ be the soft graph function of f , defined by $g(x) = (x, f(x))$ for every $x \in X$. If for each soft clopen subset (W, E) of $(X \times Y, \tau \times \tau', E)$ and for each $x \in g^{-1}(W, E)$, the set $g^{-1}(W, E) \cap f^{-1}(W_x, E)$ where (W_x, E) is a vertical cut of (W, E) at x is soft πg -open relative to $f^{-1}(W_x, E)$ then g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Proof:

Let (W, E) be any soft clopen subset of $X \times Y$ and let $x \in g^{-1}(W, E)$, be an arbitrarily chosen soft point. Then $(W, E) \cap (\{x\} \times Y)$ is soft clopen in $\{x\} \times Y$ containing $g(x)$. Also $\{x\} \times Y$ is soft homeomorphic to Y . Hence, the vertical cut $W_x = \{y \in Y: (x, y) \in (W, E)\}$ is a soft clopen subset of Y . Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(W_x, E)$ is a soft πg -open subset of X . By hypothesis $g^{-1}(W, E) \cap f^{-1}(W_x, E)$ is soft πg -open relative to $f^{-1}(W_x, E)$, so $g^{-1}(W, E) \cap f^{-1}(W_x, E)$ is soft πg -open in X . Therefore $g^{-1}(W, E)$ is soft πg -open in X . Then g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 3.17

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ and $g: (Y, \tau', E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ be functions. Then the following properties hold:

1. if f is soft πg -irresolute and g is soft slightly πg -continuous, then $g \circ f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous.
2. if f is soft πg -irresolute and g is soft πg -continuous, then $g \circ f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous.
3. if f is soft πg -irresolute and g is soft slightly continuous, then $g \circ f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 3.18

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ and $g: (Y, \tau', E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ be functions. If f is soft M - πg -open surjective and $g \circ f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous then g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Proof:

Let (A, E) be any soft clopen in Z . Since $g \circ f$ is soft slightly πg -continuous, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(A, E) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A, E))$ is soft soft πg -open. Since f is soft M - πg -open, then $f(f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A, E))) = g^{-1}(A, E)$ is soft soft πg -open in Y . Hence g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 3.19

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be surjective soft πg -irresolute, soft M - πg -open and let $g: (Y, \tau', E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ be a function. Then $g \circ f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Z, \tau'', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous if and only if g is soft slightly πg -continuous.

4. Soft πg -compact space and Soft πg -connected space

Definition: 4.1

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be soft mildly compact, if every soft clopen cover of X has a finite sub cover.

Theorem: 4.2

If a function $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous and (A, E) is soft πg -compact relative to X , then $f(A, E)$ is soft mildly compact relative to Y .

Proof:

Let $\{(V_i, E) : i \in I\}$ be any soft cover of $f(A, E)$ by soft clopen sets of the subspace $f(A, E)$. For each $i \in I$ there exists a soft clopen set (A_i, E) of Y such that $(V_i, E) = (A_i, E) \cap f(A, E)$. For each $x \in (A, E)$, there exists $i(x) \in I$ such that $f(x) \in (A_{i(x)}, E)$ and there exists $(F_x, E) \in \mathcal{S}\pi GO(X, x)$ such that $f(F_x, E) \tilde{c} (A_{i(x)}, E)$. Since the family $\{(F_x, E) : x \in (A, E)\}$ is a soft cover of (A, E) by $\mathcal{S}\pi g$ - open sets of X , there exists a finite subset (A_0, E) of (A, E) such that $(A, E) \tilde{c} \cup \{(F_x, E) : x \in (A_0, E)\}$. Hence, we obtain $f(A, E) \tilde{c} \cup \{f(F_x, E) : x \in (A_0, E)\}$ which is a subset of $\cup \{(A_{i(x)}, E) : x \in (A_0, E)\}$. Thus, $f(A, E) = \cup \{(V_{i(x)}, E) : x \in (A_0, E)\}$. Hence $f(A, E)$ is soft mildly compact relative to Y .

Corollary: 4.3

If $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous surjection and X is soft πg -compact, then Y is soft mildly compact.

Definition: 4.4

A space (X, τ, E) is said to be:

1. Soft mildly countably compact, if every soft clopen countably cover of X has a finite subcover.
2. Soft mildly Lindelöf, if every soft cover of X by soft clopen sets has a soft countable subcover.
3. Soft πg -closed compact, if every soft πg -closed cover of X has a finite subcover.
4. Soft countably πg -closed-compact, if every countable cover of X by soft πg -closed sets has a finite subcover.

Theorem: 4.5

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be a soft slightly πg -continuous surjection. Then the following statements hold:

1. If X is soft πg -Lindelöf, then Y is soft mildly Lindelöf.

2. If X is soft countably πg -compact, then Y is soft mildly countably compact.

Proof:

(1) Let $\{(V_\alpha, E) : \alpha \in I\}$ be a soft clopen cover of Y . Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, then $\{f^{-1}(V_\alpha, E) : \alpha \in I\}$ is a soft πg -open cover of X . Since X is soft πg -Lindelof, there exists a countable subset I_0 of I such that $X = \cup\{f^{-1}(V_\alpha, E) : \alpha \in I_0\}$. Thus $Y = \cup\{(V_\alpha, E) : \alpha \in I_0\}$ and hence Y is soft mildly Lindelöf. Proof of (2) Similar to (1).

Theorem: 4.6

Let $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ be a soft slightly πg -continuous surjection. Then the following statements hold:

1. If X is soft πg -closed compact, then Y is soft mildly compact.
2. If X is soft πg -closed Lindelöf, then Y is soft mildly Lindelöf.
3. If X is soft countably πg -closed compact, then Y is soft mildly countably compact.

Theorem: 4.7

If $f: (X, \tau, E) \rightarrow (Y, \tau', E)$ is soft slightly πg -continuous surjective function and X is soft πg -connected, then Y is soft connected.

Proof:

Suppose Y is not soft connected. Then there exist non-empty disjoint soft clopen subsets (U, E) and (V, E) of Y such that $Y = (U, E) \cup (V, E)$. Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, we have $f^{-1}(U, E)$ and $f^{-1}(V, E)$ are non-empty disjoint soft πg -open sets in X . Moreover, $f^{-1}(U, E) \cup f^{-1}(V, E) = X$. This shows that X is not soft πg -connected which is a contradiction. Hence Y is soft connected.

Theorem: 4.8

If f is a soft slightly πg -continuous function from a soft πg -connected space X onto any space Y , then Y is not a soft discrete space.

Proof:

Suppose that Y is soft discrete. Let (A, E) be a proper nonempty soft open subset of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A, E)$ is any proper nonempty soft πg -clopen subset of X , which is a contradiction to the assumption that X is soft πg -connected. Therefore Y is not a soft discrete space.

Theorem: 4.9

A space X is soft πg -connected, if every soft slightly πg -continuous function from a space X into any soft T_0 -space Y is constant.

Proof:

Suppose that X is not soft πg -connected. Let every soft slightly πg -continuous function from X into any soft T_0 -space then Y is constant. Since X is not soft πg -connected, there exists a proper nonempty soft πg -clopen subset (A, E) of X . Then f is a non-constant and soft slightly πg -continuous such that Y is soft $-T_0$, which is a contradiction. Hence, X is soft πg -connected.

Theorem: 4.10

If a function $f: X \rightarrow \prod Y_\alpha$ is soft slightly πg -continuous, then $P_\alpha \circ f : X \rightarrow Y_\alpha$ is soft slightly πg -continuous for each $\alpha \in \Lambda$, where P_α is the projection of $\prod Y_\alpha$ onto Y_α .

Proof:

Let (V_α, E) be any soft clopen set of Y_α . Then $P_\alpha^{-1}(V_\alpha, E)$ is soft clopen in $\prod Y_\alpha$. Hence $(P_\alpha \circ f)^{-1}(V_\alpha, E) = (f^{-1}(P_\alpha^{-1}(V_\alpha, E)))$ is soft πg -open in X . Therefore, $P_\alpha \circ f$ is soft slightly πg -continuous.

Theorem: 4.11

If a function $f: \prod X_\alpha \rightarrow \prod Y_\alpha$ is soft slightly soft πg -continuous, then $f_\alpha: X_\alpha \rightarrow Y_\alpha$ is soft slightly πg -continuous for each $\alpha \in \Lambda$.

Proof:

Let (V_α, E) be any soft clopen set of Y_α . Then $P_\alpha^{-1}(V_\alpha, E)$ is soft clopen in $\prod Y_\alpha$ and $f^{-1}(P^{-1}(V_\alpha, E)) = f^{-1}(V_\alpha, E) \times \prod \{X_\alpha : \alpha \in \Lambda \setminus \{\alpha\}\}$. Since f is soft slightly πg -continuous, $f^{-1}(P^{-1}(V_\alpha, E))$ is soft πg -open in $\prod X_\alpha$. Since the projection P_α of $\prod X_\alpha$ onto X_α is soft open and soft continuous, $f_\alpha^{-1}(V_\alpha, E)$ is soft πg -open in X_α . Hence f_α is soft slightly πg -continuous.

References

- [1] C.G. Aras and A. Sonmez, On soft mappings, arXiv: 1305.4545, (2013).
- [2] I.Arockiarani and A.Selvi, Soft πg -operators in soft topological spaces, International Journal of Mathematical archive, 5(4) 2014, 37-43.
- [3] I.Arockiarani and A.Selvi, Soft πg -continuous functions and irresolute functions, International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies, 7(2)2014, 440-446.
- [4] I.Arockiarani and A.Selvi, On soft contra πg -continuous functions, International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology, 19(2)2015, 80-90.
- [5] Athar Kharal and B. Ahmad, Mappings on soft classes, arXiv: 1006.4940(2010).
- [6] E.Ekici, On contra πg -continuous functions, Chaos Solitons and Fractals, 35(2008) 71-81.
- [7] K.Kannan, Soft Generalized closed sets in soft Topological Spaces, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, 37 (2012), 17-20.
- [8] D.Molodtsov, Soft set Theory- First Results, Computers and Mathematics with Applications (1999), 19-31.
- [9] Saziye Yuksel, Naime Tozlu, Zehra Guzel regul, On soft generalized closed sets in Soft topological Spaces, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, 37 (2012), 17-20.
- [10] M.Shabir and M. Naz , On Soft topological spaces, Computers and Mathematics with Applications 61(7)(2011), 1786-1799.
- [11] Y.Yumak, A.K. Kayamakci, Soft β -open sets and their application, arXiv: 1312.6964(2013).
- [12] I.Zortlutuna, M. Akday, W.K.Min, S.Atmaca, Remarks on soft topological spaces, Annals of fuzzy mathematical and Informatics, 3(2012) 171-185.